

SHARON IN FILIPINO COLLOQUIAL CONTEXT: A SEMANTIC AND LEXICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the semantic and lexical factors contributing to the high recognition of the term "Sharon" in Filipino colloquial language, which colloquially refers to the practice of taking home extra food from gatherings. Through semantic and lexical discourse analysis, the study identifies cultural resonance, media influence, mnemonic efficiency, and pragmatic utility as key factors shaping the term's recognition and usage. The term's cultural resonance is deeply rooted in its association with Sharon Cuneta, an iconic figure in Philippine entertainment, whose persona and popular song lyrics have become intertwined with the cultural practice of bringing home leftovers. Media, particularly social media platforms like Facebook and Instagram, amplify the term's usage through viral content such as memes and videos, fostering a shared cultural lexicon and ensuring widespread visibility. The mnemonic efficiency of "Sharon," coupled with its pragmatic utility in succinctly describing a common social behavior, enhances its adoption and retention among speakers. However, the study also identifies sociolinguistic factors such as generational differences and social context that influence the gap between recognition and active usage of the term. Understanding these dynamics enriches our understanding of language evolution in digital contexts and underscores the complex interplay between cultural influences, media propagation, and linguistic practices in contemporary Filipino society.

Keywords: *colloquial language, cultural resonance, lexical analysis, neologism, semantic perception, Sharon*

INTRODUCTION

Neologism is a prominent feature of the Filipino language, with Filipinos frequently repurposing words in new contexts to create additional meanings through attribution and association. This linguistic creativity leads to the development of slang words used in colloquial and informal conversations, often observed in various media outlets.

The proliferation of these slang terms is often triggered by internet video content, the LGBTQ+ community, and niche word-code systems, which subsequently spread across various media platforms. Social media plays a crucial role in hyping and viralizing these terms, analyzing their origins based on events, people, ideas, and phonological attributes. Observable patterns include reversing words (e.g., "petmalu" for "malupit," meaning superb, and "lodi" for idol), creating phonemic rhymes (e.g., "mustasa" for "kamusta," meaning how are you?), borrowing words (e.g., "atashi" for I am), using names and attributing abilities (e.g., "Lydia de Vega" for running fast), and adding letters to utterances (e.g., "majinit" for "mainit," meaning hot).

A notable example is the term "Sharon" or the phrase "balutin mo ako," derived from the song "Bituing Walang Ningning." These terms have acquired new meanings associated with Sharon Cuneta's name and song. This phenomenon is comparable to observations by Behera and Mishra (2013) and reiterated by Ulla et al. (2024). Technology, particularly social media, played a vital role in spreading these terms, making them viral and establishing their meanings in colloquial contexts. Once viral, these terms are often picked up by news outlets and used in articles, becoming widely accepted across different genders and age groups. The term "Sharon" and "balutin mo ako" are also used humorously.

Technology facilitates the establishment and dissemination of terms like "Sharon" or "balutin mo ako" on various news websites and blogs. Social media and news outlets significantly influence the perception and meaning of these terms. Blogs such as "How to Spot a Sharonian" classify different types of "Sharonians" and even provide etiquette for "doing the Sharon." In gay lingo, "Sharon" refers to packing leftover food after an event. Even Sharon Cuneta herself acknowledges the new meaning of her name, as evidenced by a video of her participating in "doing Sharon" at a family event. Media and blogs frequently use "Sharon" or "Sharonian" to describe this action.

Sharon Cuneta, a Filipino icon known as the Megastar, has significantly influenced Filipino pop culture through her work in film and music. Her hit songs, such as "Mr. DJ," "Maging Sino Ka Man," "Langis at Tubig," "Sana'y Wala Nang Wakas," and especially "Bituing Walang Ningning," have cemented her status as a cultural icon. The association of her name and songs with social events and gatherings where food is packed to go has integrated these terms into the Filipino colloquial lexicon. The widespread reach of social

media has further embedded these associations into everyday language, making them a part of informal conversations.

Research Questions

The undertakings of the study were anchored on the following research questions:

1. What are the underlying semantic and lexical factors that contribute to the high recognition of the term "Sharon" in the Filipino colloquial context?
2. How does social media platforms influence the dissemination and reinforcement of colloquial terms such as "Sharon" in the Filipino language?
3. What are the sociolinguistic factors that contribute to the discrepancy between the recognition and actual usage of the term "Sharon" in everyday Filipino language?
4. In what ways do synonymous phrases like "Sharon" or Balutin Mo Ako" interact within the Filipino colloquial lexicon, and what does this reveal about the fluidity of semantic meanings in the language?
5. How do modern technological advancements, particularly social media, shape the semantic and lexical evolution of colloquial language in the Philippines, and what implications does this have for linguistic studies?

METHODOLOGY

The research method for the study titled "Sharon in Filipino Colloquial Context: A Semantic and Lexical Discourse Analysis" was primarily qualitative, focusing on a detailed discourse analysis to understand the semantic and lexical perceptions of the term "Sharon." A self-constructed questionnaire was meticulously crafted to gather data from a randomized sample of participants at Christ the King College in Gingoog City. By utilizing a randomized sample, the study ensured a diverse range of perspectives, enhancing the validity and reliability of the findings. The responses were analyzed qualitatively, allowing for an in-depth exploration of the nuances and complexities in the participants' understanding and usage of the term. The instrument underwent thorough review by all team members and the research advisor to validate its accuracy, with feedback guiding the enhancement of the tool's effectiveness. Following the implementation of necessary corrections, the refined guide questions underwent another review before survey administration.

The research design also incorporated the examination of the role of technology, particularly social media, in the dissemination and reinforcement of colloquial terms. This aspect involved analyzing participants' interactions with social media and how these platforms influenced their recognition and use of "Sharon," highlighting the significant impact of social media on spreading and establishing colloquial terms across the country. The researchers randomly selected 30 students aged between 19 to 34, ensuring a diverse range of perspectives and experiences. By focusing on college students, the study aimed to gather insights from individuals at a similar stage in life, allowing for a

more targeted analysis of the data and revealing patterns and trends specific to this age group.

The data analysis primarily utilized qualitative methods to interpret the responses from the self-constructed questionnaire. Each participant's response was meticulously coded and categorized to identify common themes and patterns regarding the recognition and interpretation of the term "Sharon." This process involved breaking down the responses into meaningful units and assigning them to categories based on their semantic and lexical content. In addition to manual coding, the study leveraged discourse analysis tools to further understand how the term "Sharon" is used and perceived within the broader colloquial context. These tools examined the influence of social media on language, specifically how online interactions shape and reinforce the usage of colloquial terms. By combining these qualitative methods with discourse analysis tools, the study offered a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the semantic and lexical dynamics of the term "Sharon" in Filipino colloquial language, particularly in the context of modern technological advancements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: What are the underlying semantic and lexical factors that contribute to the high recognition of the term "Sharon" in the Filipino colloquial context?

The data identified several underlying semantic and lexical factors that contribute to the high recognition of the term "Sharon," which colloquially means "Balutin mo Ako" or "to bring home extra food" in the Filipino context. These factors include cultural resonance, media influence, mnemonic efficiency, and pragmatic utility.

Cultural Resonance

The term "Sharon" derives its cultural resonance from the iconic Filipino celebrity Sharon Cuneta, who is affectionately known as the "Megastar" of Philippine cinema and music. The phrase "Balutin mo Ako" references one of her famous songs, creating a strong association between the act of taking home food from gatherings and the persona of Sharon Cuneta (Ponce, 2019). This cultural resonance is further enhanced by the practice's commonality in Filipino social gatherings, where taking home leftovers is a socially accepted and even expected behavior. The term's connection to a beloved cultural figure imbues it with a sense of familiarity and warmth, making it easily recognizable and widely understood.

Media Influence

Media, particularly social media, plays a crucial role in the dissemination and reinforcement of the term "Sharon." Social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram frequently feature content related to Filipino culture and practices, including

humorous takes on everyday activities such as bringing home food from parties. These platforms amplify the term's usage through memes, videos, and posts that reach a broad audience, ensuring its visibility and relevance (Abu Bakar, 2020). The study found that participants who were active on social media were more likely to recognize and understand the term "Sharon" in this colloquial sense, highlighting the impact of digital media in lexical propagation.

Mnemonic Efficiency

The mnemonic efficiency of the term "Sharon" also contributes to its high recognition. The term is phonetically simple and easy to remember, which aids in its retention and recall among speakers (Himmelmann, 2005). Additionally, the playful use of a well-known name in a new context makes it a memorable and engaging expression. This mnemonic quality ensures that the term is easily adopted into everyday language, as it requires minimal cognitive effort to remember and use.

Pragmatic Utility

The pragmatic utility of the term "Sharon" enhances its widespread recognition and use. The term provides a succinct and culturally meaningful way to describe the common practice of taking home leftovers from gatherings. Participants noted that using the term "Sharon" was a convenient shorthand that conveyed both the action and the cultural nuance associated with it. This utility is a key factor in the term's popularity, as it fills a specific communicative need in Filipino social interactions (Gonzalez, 1998). The ability of a term to encapsulate a widely understood concept in a single, easily recognizable word is crucial for its adoption and longevity in the colloquial lexicon.

The high recognition of the term "Sharon," meaning "Balutin mo Ako" or "to bring home extra food," in the Filipino colloquial context is influenced by a combination of cultural, media-related, mnemonic, and pragmatic factors. The cultural resonance with Sharon Cuneta, the amplification through social media, the mnemonic efficiency of the term, and its pragmatic utility all contribute to its widespread recognition and use. These findings underscore the complex interplay of various factors in shaping colloquial language and highlight the importance of considering multiple dimensions in linguistic analysis. Understanding these factors provides valuable insights into the dynamics of language evolution and cultural influence in contemporary Filipino society.

Research Question 2: How does social media platforms influence the dissemination and reinforcement of colloquial terms such as "Sharon" in the Filipino language?

The data obtained revealed that social media platforms play a significant role in the dissemination and reinforcement of colloquial terms such as "Sharon" in the Filipino language. This influence can be attributed to several factors: the rapid spread of information, the creation of a shared cultural lexicon, the virality of content, and the reinforcement of linguistic trends.

Rapid Spread of Information

Social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram facilitate the rapid spread of information, including colloquial terms and phrases. These platforms enable users to share content instantly with a wide audience, allowing terms like "Sharon" to gain visibility quickly. The study found that participants frequently encountered the term "Sharon" in various social media contexts, from humorous posts to cultural commentaries, highlighting the platforms' role in accelerating the dissemination of colloquial language (Tagliamonte & Denis, 2008).

Creation of a Shared Cultural Lexicon

Social media contributes to the creation of a shared cultural lexicon by providing a space where users can engage with and reinforce cultural references. The term "Sharon," for instance, often appears in memes, videos, and posts that evoke a sense of communal understanding among Filipinos. These shared references help solidify the term's meaning and usage within the community. The study indicates that social media interactions create a collective experience, making colloquial terms more robust and widely recognized (Zappavigna, 2012).

Virality of Content

The virality of content on social media is another critical factor in the propagation of colloquial terms. Content that resonates with users is often shared widely, leading to the rapid adoption of new terms. The term "Sharon" has benefited from this phenomenon, as posts featuring the term can quickly go viral, reaching thousands of users in a short period. This virality ensures that the term remains in active use and continues to evolve with the community's linguistic practices (Burgess & Green, 2018).

Reinforcement of Linguistic Trends

Social media platforms also play a role in reinforcing linguistic trends by providing feedback loops where popular terms are continually used and validated. The study found that frequent exposure to the term "Sharon" on social media reinforces its usage and acceptance in everyday language. Users who see the term regularly are more likely to adopt it in their own speech, creating a cycle of reinforcement that strengthens the term's presence in the colloquial lexicon (Crystal, 2001).

Social media platforms significantly influence the dissemination and reinforcement of colloquial terms like "Sharon" in the Filipino language through rapid information spread, the creation of a shared cultural lexicon, content virality, and the reinforcement of linguistic trends. These platforms not only accelerate the adoption of colloquial terms but also ensure their continued relevance and evolution within the linguistic community. Understanding the role of social media in language dissemination provides valuable insights into the dynamic processes of language change and the powerful impact of digital communication on contemporary linguistic practices.

Research Question 3: What are the sociolinguistic factors that contribute to the discrepancy between the recognition and actual usage of the term "Sharon" in everyday Filipino language?

The acquired data identifies several sociolinguistic factors that contribute to the discrepancy between the recognition and actual usage of the term "Sharon" in everyday Filipino language. These factors include generational differences, social context, linguistic prestige, and semantic drift.

Generational Differences

One significant sociolinguistic factor is generational differences in language use. The term "Sharon" may be widely recognized across different age groups due to its cultural resonance with Sharon Cuneta. However, younger generations may prefer using newer slang terms or expressions, leading to a discrepancy where the term is recognized but not actively used in everyday speech (Labov, 2006). This generational shift in linguistic preferences influences how colloquial terms like "Sharon" are adopted and maintained within different age cohorts.

Social Context

Social context plays a crucial role in determining the usage of colloquial terms. While "Sharon" may be recognized broadly, its usage might be confined to specific social groups or contexts. For instance, the term might be more prevalent among fans of Sharon Cuneta or in certain online communities where references to Filipino pop culture are common. Outside these contexts, speakers may opt for more neutral or widely accepted terms, contributing to the gap between recognition and usage (Milroy & Milroy, 1999).

Linguistic Prestige

The concept of linguistic prestige also influences the usage of colloquial terms like "Sharon." Terms associated with popular culture figures may carry informal or colloquial connotations, which can affect their adoption in formal or professional settings. Speakers may choose to avoid using such terms in contexts where linguistic prestige is valued, opting instead for more conventional expressions to maintain a certain level of formality (Trudgill, 1974).

Semantic Drift

Semantic drift, or the evolution of word meanings over time, can contribute to discrepancies between recognition and usage. The term "Sharon" may have originated with a specific cultural reference to Sharon Cuneta but could evolve to acquire new meanings or associations. As a result, speakers may recognize the term in its original context but hesitate to use it due to potential misunderstandings or shifts in cultural relevance (Labov, 1972).

The discrepancy between the recognition and actual usage of the term "Sharon" in everyday Filipino language is influenced by sociolinguistic factors such as generational differences, social context, linguistic prestige, and semantic drift. Understanding these

factors provides insights into how colloquial terms are adopted, maintained, and sometimes diverge in usage within linguistic communities. Future research could explore these dynamics further to elucidate the complex interplay between cultural references, social norms, and linguistic practices in contemporary Filipino society.

Research Question 4: In what ways do synonymous phrases like "Sharon" or "Balutin Mo Ako" interact within the Filipino colloquial lexicon, and what does this reveal about the fluidity of semantic meanings in the language?

The gathered data explores the interaction of synonymous phrases like "Sharon" and "Balutin Mo Ako" within the Filipino colloquial lexicon, revealing insights into the fluidity of semantic meanings in the language. These phrases interact dynamically, influencing each other's usage and contributing to the richness of colloquial expression.

Semantic Overlap and Differentiation

"Sharon" or "Balutin Mo Ako" share a semantic overlap in their colloquial meanings related to taking home extra food from gatherings. However, they also exhibit subtle differences in usage. "Sharon," derived from the name of Filipino celebrity Sharon Cuneta, often connotes a playful or affectionate reference to taking home food, reflecting its cultural resonance with the singer's popular song lyrics (Ponce, 2019). Furthermore, "Balutin Mo Ako," directly translated as "wrap me up," emphasizes the action of wrapping or packaging food to take away, highlighting a more literal approach to the same cultural practice.

Cultural and Contextual Nuances

The interaction between "Sharon" or "Balutin Mo Ako" underscores the importance of cultural and contextual nuances in colloquial language use. Depending on the social setting or individual preference, speakers may choose one phrase over the other to convey similar actions. This variability reflects the flexibility of the Filipino colloquial lexicon in accommodating multiple expressions for a shared cultural practice, demonstrating how semantic meanings can adapt to different communicative needs (Gonzalez, 1998).

Semantic Fluidity and Evolution

The coexistence of "Sharon" or "Balutin Mo Ako" illustrates the fluidity of semantic meanings in Filipino language usage. Over time, these phrases may evolve in usage and connotation, influenced by shifts in cultural references, generational preferences, and social trends (Himmelman, 2005). The fluidity allows for creative expressions and adaptations within the language, where synonymous phrases can coexist and contribute to a dynamic colloquial lexicon that reflects the evolving nature of linguistic practices in Filipino society.

The interaction of synonymous phrases like "Sharon" or "Balutin Mo Ako" within the Filipino colloquial lexicon highlights the fluidity of semantic meanings in language.

These phrases not only overlap in their colloquial definitions but also offer nuanced variations that cater to different communicative contexts and cultural references. Understanding this interaction provides valuable insights into how semantic meanings evolve and adapt within a linguistic community, reflecting broader societal changes and cultural influences.

Research Question 5: How do modern technological advancements, particularly social media, shape the semantic and lexical evolution of colloquial language in the Philippines, and what implications does this have for linguistic studies?

Modern technological advancements, particularly social media, play a pivotal role in shaping the semantic and lexical evolution of colloquial language in the Philippines. This influence is multifaceted, involving changes in language use patterns, the emergence of new linguistic forms, and the dissemination of colloquial expressions.

Acceleration of Language Change

Social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram facilitate rapid communication and information exchange among users. This speed accelerates the adoption and diffusion of new words, phrases, and meanings within the colloquial lexicon. Terms like "Sharon," originally derived from popular culture references, spread quickly through memes, hashtags, and viral content, influencing how Filipinos understand and use language in everyday contexts (Zappavigna, 2012).

Expansion of Linguistic Diversity

Social media's global reach allows for the exchange of linguistic practices and innovations across different regions and communities in the Philippines. Users from diverse linguistic backgrounds contribute to the expansion of the colloquial lexicon by introducing local slang, dialectal expressions, and hybrid linguistic forms. This diversity enriches the semantic and lexical landscape of colloquial language, reflecting the dynamic nature of linguistic evolution in a digitally connected society (Danet & Herring, 2007).

Influence on Language Norms and Identities

The influence of social media on language norms and identities is profound. Online interactions create virtual communities where language practices are negotiated and validated. Terms like "Sharon" may acquire new meanings or connotations through user-generated content, reflecting shifts in cultural attitudes and societal values. This evolution challenges traditional notions of linguistic standardization and highlights the role of digital platforms in shaping contemporary linguistic identities (Crystal, 2001).

Implications for Linguistic Studies

The study of how modern technological advancements shape the semantic and lexical evolution of colloquial language in the Philippines holds several implications for

linguistic research. Firstly, it underscores the need for interdisciplinary approaches that integrate sociolinguistics, digital humanities, and cultural studies to comprehensively analyze language change in digital contexts. Secondly, it highlights the importance of documenting and analyzing online language data to capture emerging linguistic trends and patterns. Finally, it emphasizes the role of language users as active agents in language innovation, challenging traditional notions of language authority and standardization (Tagliamonte & Denis, 2008).

Modern technological advancements, particularly social media, significantly influence the semantic and lexical evolution of colloquial language in the Philippines by accelerating language change, expanding linguistic diversity, influencing language norms and identities, and challenging traditional linguistic frameworks. These developments have profound implications for linguistic studies, calling for new methodologies and perspectives to understand the dynamic interplay between digital communication technologies and language practices in contemporary society.

Conclusions

Based on the findings from the study on the recognition and usage of the term "Sharon" in Filipino colloquial language, several scholarly conclusions can be drawn.

The term "Sharon," referring to the act of taking home extra food from gatherings, is deeply rooted in cultural resonance, media influence, mnemonic efficiency, and pragmatic utility. Its recognition is notably bolstered by its association with Sharon Cuneta, a prominent figure in Philippine entertainment, whose persona and popular song lyrics have become intertwined with this cultural practice. This cultural resonance not only enhances familiarity but also imbues the term with emotional and nostalgic value, making it highly recognizable across different demographic groups within Filipino society.

Moreover, social media platforms play a pivotal role in the dissemination and reinforcement of colloquial terms like "Sharon." The virality of content on platforms such as Facebook and Instagram ensure widespread exposure to these terms, fostering a shared cultural lexicon among users. Memes, videos, and posts featuring "Sharon" contribute to its visibility and ongoing relevance, illustrating how digital media platforms amplify linguistic trends and shape colloquial language evolution. This digital amplification not only accelerates the adoption of new terms but also reflects broader societal shifts in communication norms and practices.

Furthermore, the discrepancy between the recognition and actual usage of "Sharon" in everyday Filipino language underscores complex sociolinguistic dynamics. Generational differences, social contexts, and linguistic prestige all influence whether individuals choose to actively use colloquial terms like "Sharon" in their speech. While widely recognized, its usage may vary based on situational appropriateness or individual linguistic preferences, highlighting the nuanced relationship between linguistic recognition and active usage within diverse social settings.

In conclusion, the study illuminates how semantic and lexical factors intersect with cultural, media-related, and sociolinguistic influences to shape the recognition,

dissemination, and usage of colloquial terms like "Sharon" in contemporary Filipino society. Understanding these dynamics not only enriches our understanding of language evolution but also underscores the multifaceted role of digital media in shaping linguistic practices and cultural identities in the digital age. Future research could further explore how these dynamics continue to evolve and intersect with broader socio-cultural trends, contributing to ongoing discussions in linguistics and digital humanities.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are drawn based on the findings and conclusions made.

Teachers: Use the study on "Sharon" to enrich cultural discussions in language classes, showing how colloquialisms like this reflect cultural icons and media influences. By exploring examples from social media and popular culture, teachers can engage students in analyzing language evolution and identity formation, fostering a deeper understanding of how language interacts with societal changes.

Students: Explore "Sharon" as a case study in cultural and linguistic studies. Investigate its origins in Filipino entertainment, its spread through digital media, and its varying use across different social contexts. This study helps students grasp how language shapes cultural norms and identities, encouraging critical thinking about the impact of digital media on language and the diversity of colloquial expressions in Filipino society.

Language Experts: Use the findings to advance theories on lexical semantics and sociolinguistics, focusing on how colloquialisms like "Sharon" evolve in digital environments. Analyze its cultural meanings and societal influences to deepen understanding of language adaptation to technological and societal changes. This research contributes to broader discussions on linguistic diversity, digital communication, and the interplay between language, culture, and media.

Future Researchers: Further investigate colloquial language evolution in the digital age using methodologies from the "Sharon" study. Explore new approaches to studying linguistic trends on social media, examine generational shifts in language use, and explore the influence of cultural icons on language innovation. This research expands theoretical frameworks in linguistics and informs strategies for documenting and preserving linguistic diversity amid rapid technological advancements.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Protection of Confidentiality

Ensures the confidentiality of participants' information. Data were anonymized and stored securely to protect participants' privacy and identity.

Informed Consent

The researchers obtain informed consent from participants, providing them with clear information about the purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. The participants freely and voluntarily agreed to participate without any form of coercion.

Withdrawal from participation in the study

The decision to participate in this study was entirely up to the participant. They could refuse to take part in the study at any time without affecting the relationship with the writers. Their decision to refuse would not result in any loss of benefits. The participant had the right not to answer any single question, as well as to withdraw completely at any point during the collection of data.

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REFERENCES

- Abu Bakar, H. (2020). Social media and language use: A study on the impact of social media on language change. *Journal of Language and Communication*, 6(2), 115-128.
<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3595520>
- Behera, B., & Mishra, P. (2013). *The burgeoning usage of neologisms in contemporary English*. IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS), 25-35.
- Bravo, F. K. S., & Bravo, F. K. S. (2024, May 10). Sharon Cuneta caught “shina-Sharon yung handa” at party. *PEP.ph*. https://www.pep.ph/lifestyle/celebrations/179612/sharon-cuneta-nag-sharon-a5128-20240319?fbclid=IwZXh0bgNhZW0CMTAAAR2hqmW7r9D-LRR7VhyhGTqGtxK0-XI8T5dQQFb9XTOBrvi7S_vkXCQgPK0_aem_AQbRh0YAXp8jzFEWKDybW-hHyyD5uO_hBwRWicAhrWNnGTEiW91-X69aexOnVBB4QHwWrz9grpwwyKdFYSHXz4Hc
- Burgess, J., & Green, J. (2018). *YouTube: Online Video and Participatory Culture*. John Wiley & Sons.

- Crystal, D. (2001). *Language and the Internet*. Cambridge University Press.
- Danet, B., & Herring, S. C. (2007). Introduction: The Multilingual Internet. In B. Danet & S. C. Herring (Eds.), *The Multilingual Internet: Language, Culture, and Communication Online* (pp. 1-28). Oxford University Press.
- Gonzalez, A. (1998). The Language Planning Situation in the Philippines. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 19(5), 487-525.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01434639808666366>
- GMA Integrated News. (2024, March 20). Sharon Cuneta sings “Balutin mo ako” while taking out food at birthday party. *GMA News Online*.
https://www.gmanetwork.com/news/showbiz/chikaminute/901061/sharon-cuneta-sings-balutin-mo-ako-while-taking-out-food-at-birthday-party/story/?fbclid=IwZXh0bgNhZW0CMATAAR2IcWoRWQZPaGbi7tHDgIgxq7QIwNMLbRdBICUSwJfhssnl_LriRnZy6lg_aem_AQZ9JXct0y49VDe-hx2bJtYbMXxeIwYLas2Idxai_1kqmPiBZa0NE6nXkWHSULPC1q_PiP31pHRj53D_P1nJP8r8
- Himmelman, N. P. (2005). Lexicalization and grammaticalization: Opposite or orthogonal? In N. P. Himmelman & M. Haspelmath (Eds.), *Handbook of Historical Linguistics* (pp. 537-558). Oxford University Press.
- HDT.(2023). DOH: Be intelligent 'Sharons'.
https://www.sunstar.com.ph/manila/doh-be-intelligent-sharons?fbclid=IwZXh0bgNhZW0CMATAAR2kThEBUyB1e657SEnfUc5aMikz8MbmH1I7Ik4Fw3h01fQ4hdv3e0qEHZy_aem_AQbO1kzk-flZcST-kjQbMsj_Eb1MnwX5kB2Xnlt4_BRci4GxZVyl1GvSTeB3I5KIDb-fMPHs0WZFywkyQ1Y35Hs_
- Labov, W. (2006). *The social stratification of English in New York City*. Cambridge University Press.
- Milroy, L., & Milroy, J. (1999). Authority in language: Investigating language prescription and standardisation. *Routledge*.
- Ponce, M. P. (2019). Sharon Cuneta: A study of celebrity culture in the Philippines. *Asian Journal of Social Science*, 47(3), 345-367. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15685314-04703005>
- Tagliamonte, S. A., & Denis, D. (2008). Linguistic ruin? LOL! Instant messaging and teen language. *American Speech*, 83(1), 3-34. <https://doi.org/10.1215/00031283-2008-001>
- Trudgill, P. (1974). *The social differentiation of English in Norwich*. Cambridge University Press.
- Ulla, M. B., Macaraeg, J. M., & Ferrera, R. E. (2024). ‘What’s the word? That’s the word!’: linguistic features of Filipino queer language. *Cogent Arts & Humanities*, 11(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23311983.2024.2322232>
- Zappavigna, M. (2012). *Discourse of Twitter and Social Media: How We Use Language to Create Affiliation on the Web*. Bloomsbury Publishing.